

Preparation and Characterization of Silver Nanoparticles for Enzymatic Inhibition of Pepsin in Anti-HIV Drug Discovery

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ABSTRACT

The present study focuses on the Preparation and Characterization of Silver Nanoparticles (AgNPs) for Enzymatic Inhibition of Pepsin in Anti-HIV Drug Discovery. Silver nanoparticles have gained significant attention as potential bioactive agents due to their unique physicochemical and biological properties. In this work, AgNPs were synthesized using a green and chemical reduction approach employing silver nitrate as a precursor and suitable reducing and stabilizing agents to ensure controlled particle size and stability. The synthesized nanoparticles were characterized by UV-Visible spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, X-ray Diffraction (XRD), and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) to determine their size, morphology, crystallinity, and surface functional groups. The study highlights the dual functionality of silver nanoparticles as enzyme modulators and potential carriers for targeted drug delivery, paving the way for future investigations into nanoparticle-assisted antiviral therapy.

Keywords: AgNPs, Nanoparticle, Antiviral, Characterization.

INTRODUCTION

Nanomaterials and nanoparticles are finding new uses in a variety of industries at a rapid rate. The distinct physicochemical properties of nanoparticles, such as visual, catalytic, and Both the specific surface area and the proportion of surface atoms are large in metal nanoparticles. Scientists are becoming interested in their innovative synthesis techniques due to its electrical, antimicrobial, and magnetic qualities. The human herpes virus family, Herpes viridae, includes Herpes simplex viruses 1 and 2 (HSV-1 and HSV-2). HSV-1, which causes the majority of cold sores, and HSV-2, which causes the majority of genital herpes, are both communicable. When an infected person produces and sheds the virus, they can spread. Sharing drinks is one way that herpes simplex can be transmitted through contact with saliva. (1-4)

Material And Method:

Preparation of Solutions: -

Molarity is equal to moles/ liter

Molar mass of $\text{AgNO}_3 = 169.87 \sim 170 \text{g/mol}$

1M solution of $\text{AgNO}_3 = 169.87 \sim 170 \text{g/L}$

1. Preparation of 100ml 1mM silver nitrate solution:

- 0.017g of AgNO_3 was added to 100ml volumetric flask.
- Enough deionised water was added to dissolve.
- Then water was added to make up volume.

2. For preparation of 10ml 10mM Trisodium citrate solution:

- 0.025807g of Trisodium citrate was added to 10ml volumetric flask.
- Enough deionised water was added to dissolve.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

- Then water was added to make up volume.

3. For preparation of 100ml 1mM valacyclovir solution:

- 0.0324g of valacyclovir was added to 100ml volumetric flask.
- Enough deionized water was added to dissolve.
- Then water was added to make up volume.

Procedure: (5,6,7)

For preparation of silver nano-particles of valacyclovir

1. 1mM solution of valacyclovir 100ml was taken.
2. 1mM solution of AgNO₃ 100ml was taken mixed both the solution stirred it for 1hr using magnetic stirrer at 1000rpm maintained at 100°C.
3. After 1hr 10mM solution of citrate 10ml was added dropwise 1drop/sec and continued stirring for further 2hr.
4. Afterwards kept aside undisturbed for 18hrs.
5. On next day the same solution was centrifuged at 20,000rpm for 15min.
6. Solid was collected and dried to get silver nanoparticles of valacyclovir.

2. Materials And Methods

2.1 Chemical required:

Enzyme Pepsin (Himedia), Hemoglobin (Himedia), Valacyclovir, Silver nanoparticle of valacyclovir, Sodium Acetate tri hydrates (Qualigens), Sodium Chloride (Himedia), Tri Chloro Acetic acid (TCA) (Sdfine). Acetate buffer was prepared by 50 Mm Na Acetate tri hydrate and 0.1 M NaCl with pH- 3.5.

2.2 Instruments required

Spectrophotometer - Karry 100, Rami for 8000 rpm, Micropipette 5-40 µl, 40-200 µl, 200-1000 µl, Eppendorff (1.75ml), electronic balance.

2.3 Enzyme Pepsin activity inhibition Assay: - Pepsin has a quite close resemblance in proteolytic activity with HIV-1 protease one of key enzyme of HIV-1 life cycle as both of them belong to same Aspartate enzyme family. This enzyme was used as a substitute of HIV-1 protease to check out anti-HIV

activity of valacyclovir and silver nanoparticle of valacyclovir in this experiment.

2.4 Procedure (8)

Enzyme inhibition assay

Protease has a quite resemblance in proteolytic activity with HIV-protease one key enzyme of HIV-1 life cycle as both of them belongs to same aspartate enzyme family¹⁸. This enzyme was used as a substitute of HIV-1 protease to check out anti- HIV activity of silver nanoparticle of valacyclovir in the present investigation. The inhibition of protease enzyme is measured (Sigma Aldrich) using their corresponding substrate (Sigma Aldrich).

1. For this assay, 50µg pepsin, 800µg hemoglobin and different crude plant extracts were taken in 500µl of reaction mixture.
2. The mixture was allowed to incubate at 37°C, after 20 min 700µl of 5% TCA was added to stop the reaction.
3. It was then centrifuged at 14000 g for 5 min and the supernatant was collected.
4. Optical Density (OD) was recorded spectrophotometrically at 280 nm. Separate blanks were used or both positive and negative controls as well as for sample.
5. For negative control, enzyme and substrate were taken and followed the above procedure and for positive control protease was taken as a well-known inhibitor of HIV-protease, lopinavir was taken as positive control.
6. Each sample was taken in triplicate, so this assay gives reproducible results.

Percentage of inhibition was calculated by using a formula. Inhibition (%) = [(OD of negative control - OD of sample) / OD of negative control] × 100(85).

Several experiments were performed to get optimum activity of enzyme:

Table No.1 Parameter used in experiment

Parameter	Optimum range
p ^H	2- 4
Incubation period	30min.
Reaction volume	1000 µL
Incubation temperature	37 ° C
Centrifugation	14000 rpm.

CHARACTERIZATION OF NANOPARTICLES (9,10,11)

1. Physical Appearance:

The Organoleptic properties of the Nanoparticles, like colour, odour and physical appearance were checked by visual observation. Colour was found to be Brownish and odour was metallic.

Table.No.2 Physical Appearance of Valacyclovir silver nano particles

Organoleptic properties	Observation
Colour	Brownish black
Odour	Metallic

Figure.1 Physical Appearance of valacyclovir silver nano particles

2. Determination of Practical Yield:

Practical yield=100mg

Theoretical yield=230mg

Percentage yield= $100/230 * 100 = 43.47\%$

3. Particle Size Analysis: -

Figure.2 Particle Size of valacyclovir silver nano particles

Figure.3 Intensity of Particle Size of valacyclovir silver nano particles

Table No.3 Intensity of Particle Size of Val acyclovir silver nano particles

Sr.no	Particle size	Intensity
1	10	0
2	20	1
3	30	2
4	40	1
5	50	2
6	60	8
7	70	2
8	80	1
9	90	2
10	100	1

4. UV/ Vis Spectroscopy Analysis (12,13)

In metal nano particles such as in silver, the conduction band and valence band lie very close to each other in which electrons move freely. These free electrons give rise to a surface plasmon resonance (SPR) absorption band occurring due to the collective oscillation of electrons of silver nano particles in resonance with the light wave. Classically, the electric field of an incoming wave induces a polarization of the electrons with respect to much heavier ionic core of silver nanoparticles. As a result, a net charge difference occurs which in turn acts as a restoring force? This creates a dipolar oscillation of all the electrons with the same phase. When the frequency of

the electromagnetic field becomes resonant with the coherent electron motion, a strong absorption takes place, which is the origin of the observed colour. Here the colour of the prepared silver nanoparticles is dark brownish black.

This absorption strongly depends on the particle size, dielectric medium and chemical surroundings. The UV/Vis absorption spectra of the silver nano particles dispersed in distilled water is shown in the figure below. The absorption peak (SPR) is obtained in the visible range at 255 nm. With the above-mentioned concentration. The stability of silver nanoparticles is observed for 4months and it shows a SPR peak at the same wavelength.

Figure.4 UV/ Vis Spectra of valacyclovir

Figure.5 UV/ Vis Spectra of valacyclovir silver nanoparticles

5. Powder X-ray Diffraction Analysis (14,15)

The structure of prepared silver nanoparticles has been investigated by X-ray diffraction (XRD)

analysis. Typical XRD patterns of the sample, prepared by the present chemical method are shown in the Fig. 6 and 7

Figure.6 X-ray diffraction pattern of Valacyclovir

The XRD study indicates the formation of silver (Ag) nano particles.

Figure.7 X-ray diffraction pattern of silver nano particles of Valacyclovir

The XRD result shows four distinct diffraction peaks at 38.12° , 44.27° , 64.27° and 76.23° , which are indexed for the planes (111), (200), (220) and (311) respectively of the face centered cubic Ag (fig. 12). This data was matched with the database of joint committee on powder diffraction standards (JCPDS) for silver. Thus, the formation of Ag is confirmed.

6. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM): (16)

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is an electron optical imaging technique that provides photographic images and elemental information. The signals that derive from electron sample interactions reveal information about the sample including external morphology (texture) and crystalline structure and orientation of materials making up the sample. Used to determine particle size distribution, surface topography, texture and examine the morphology of fractured or sectioned surface.

Figure.8 SEM of valacyclovir silver nano particles

7. Infrared Analysis:

The FTIR spectra are used to identify the drug and help to detect the interaction of drug with polymers. FTIR spectrum of pure drug and optimized

nanoparticles prepared batch were obtained on FTIR (Bruker Alpha-T, India) instrument. The spectrum of nanoparticles optimized batch was taken. The spectrum was scanned over the wave number range of $3600-500\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Figure.9 FTIR spectrum of valacyclovir

Figure.10 FTIR spectrum of valacyclovir silver nano particles

Table No.4 Functional Group in FTIR spectrum of valacyclovir silver nano particles

Peak Name	Center	Functional Group
Peak 1	1070.77	C-O Alcohols, Ethers, Esters, Carboxylic Acids, Anhydrides
Peak 2	1437.33	-CH ₃ (bend)
Peak 3	1565.97	N-H Primary and Secondary Amines and Amides
Peak 4	1648.22	C=C Alkene
Peak 5	2098.92	X=C=Y Allenes, Ketenes, Isocyanates, Isothiocyanates
Peak 6	3278.53	O-H Alcohols, Phenols

8. Differential Scanning Calorimeter Analysis:

Determine the enthalpy of melting (fusion) and the heat capacity, glass transition temperature, and the change in heat capacity for the glass transition. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) monitors heat effects associated with phase transitions and Chemical reactions as a function of temperature. In a DSC the difference in heat flow to the sample and a

reference at the same temperature, is recorded as a function of Temperature. Thermo grams of Valacyclovir silver nanoparticles were obtained using DSC Scanning up to 454°C.

Figure.11 Differential Scanning Calorimeter Analysis

Table no. 5 Comparative % Inhibition of Lopinavir, Silver Nanoparticle of Valacyclovir, and Valacyclovir at 1 mM Concentration"

Sr. no.	Compound	Concentration	Reading	% Inhibition
1	Lopinavir (std)	1 mM	1.0113	100
2	Silver nano particle of valacyclovir	1mM	0.6154	60.85
3	Valacyclovir	1mM	0.51	50.43

DISCUSSION:

Anti-HIV activity was evaluated by using pepsin enzyme. Silver nano particle of valacyclovir at conc. 1mM have shown inhibitory activity with 60.85 % and pure Valacyclovir at conc. 1mM have shown inhibitory activity with 50.43%. From these results we confirmed the protease inhibitor property of silver nano particle of valacyclovir compound is 10% more than that of pure Valacyclovir and it acts as an inhibitor for the pepsin enzyme; further studies are needed to know the mechanism of silver nano particle of valacyclovir on the protease enzyme as an inhibitor.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that no Conflict of Interest to this work.

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